

Least Squares Approximation-based Polynomial Chaos Expansion for Uncertainty Quantification and Robust Optimization in Aeronautics

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For many engineering problems, reliability and robustness are far more important than the nominal performance when it comes to the choice of a design over another. Availability of state-of-the-art simulation codes and trusted modeling approaches help in reducing the epistemic uncertainties, but what is needed for decision-making is ultimately the knowledge of the aleatory uncertainty for the system of interest, and methods capable of minimizing such uncertainty while limiting the impact on the expected performance. A reliable measure of performance is only achieved if all uncertainties affecting the system's geometry, physical properties and operational conditions can be propagated through the model equations to the quantities of interest. Optimization in a deterministic sense, providing the best possible performance for nominal values of the design variables, is then replaced by Robust Optimization, which aims at maximizing the expected performance while minimizing the probability of its degradation. Today, multi-physics problems and demanding high-fidelity simulations are common denominators in Aeronautics as well as in many other industrial fields. It is then necessary to employ techniques that are able to perform uncertainty quantification and propagation at reasonable costs, without requiring the development of dedicated solvers: Non-Intrusive Polynomial Chaos is a prime candidate, but not all of its variants are equally accurate and cost-effective. Efficiency and flexibility of Least Squares surrogates and gradient-enhanced Polynomial Chaos expansions for Uncertainty Quantification and Robust Optimization are discussed in this paper employing an in-house framework. Advantages of the proposed methods over Collocation approaches are demonstrated by comparing the results for a selection of algebraic test cases and for the shape optimization of the NACA 0012 airfoil under transonic conditions.

I. Introduction

The performance of all engineering systems is affected by some degree of uncertainty. For instance, manufacturing tolerances as well as deterioration of the components over time naturally make the parameters describing its geometry uncertain variables. At the same time, operational conditions are not going to exactly match the assumptions made during the design process. In general any system, be it a turbomachinery stage, a wing or the avionics of an aircraft, will be affected by a wide range of uncertainties. The performance is quantified evaluating one or more quantities of interest (QoIs), which depend on the deterministic response of the system to the uncertain design variables. If uncertainty is not taken into account and only nominal values are considered, any performance metrics will exhibit some deviations with respect to the estimated performance or even severe degradation in real life. Here, the focus is not on the epistemic component of uncertainty ([1] and references therein), involving the mathematical and physical models in use and the numerical tools employed for solving their equations: the paper only deals with aleatory uncertainty, representing the main area of application for stochastic methods when dealing with performance evaluation and design optimization.

Uncertainty quantification (UQ) allows us to evaluate an existing design in search for the causes of performance degradation. The focus is on the knowledge about how much the expected performance (in a probabilistic sense)

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deviates from the deterministic prediction based on nominal values of the design variables. Just as important is the range of variability of the performance for a given design, quantified by its variance or standard deviation, and providing a measure of its robustness. In addition, great advantage can derive from knowing the gradients of the mean value and standard deviation of the performance with respect to the design variables (i.e., the moments' sensitivities): they carry the fundamental information needed to drive a gradient-based optimization under uncertainty when the robustness itself must be included in the objective.

When UQ is not available, only deterministic optimization (DO) can be performed. The best design maximizing the performance can be sought, but it is not possible to know in advance how much that performance will be degraded in response to even the least variations in geometrical dimensions of the components, physical conditions to which the system is subjected, influence of the surrounding environment, and so on. More importantly, the optimization process cannot be forced to consider this crucial factor from the beginning and to direct the research of the optimum accordingly, what is possible with robust optimization (RO). RO requires the engineer to choose which balance between the expected value for the performance and its robustness is to be pursued, for instance by assigning different weights to the mean and standard deviation of the QoIs. Since every step in the optimization process in RO involves UQ, the employed UQ method is expected to play the most significant role in determining expensiveness of the optimization. Polynomial Chaos expansion (PCE) provides a metamodel for the QoI. In a deterministic context, the mapping from the variables of the system to its response in the form of a set of equations is exactly known, and the variables are treated as observable quantities. The same (deterministic) mapping in presence of uncertain variables gives raise to a stochastic response, dependent on their probability distributions. The QoI becomes a random variable, for which PCE gives a functional representation by projection on a basis of orthogonal polynomials. The metamodel is complete if the coefficients combining the basis elements are known. If one of the so-called Non-Intrusive Polynomial Chaos (NIPC) methods is employed, computation of the coefficients requires a number of training simulations - or evaluations, if the deterministic mapping involves only algebraic functions -, on a set of points extracted from the joint probability density function of the uncertain variables. Many research efforts are devoted to make the number of points as small as possible, and alternative NIPC methods essentially differ, from a practical standpoint, for how they choose them and what degree of accuracy are able to provide given the number. Among the most common NIPC methods, Least Squares surrogates are especially valued for their flexibility and overall efficiency. Their choice, together with the concept of gradient-enhanced Polynomial Chaos, enables cost-effective solutions for UQ. Their nature of surrogates puts the basis for further efficiency improvements in the context of robust optimization, like the reuse of points that is going to be discussed and applied in the following.

This paper is structured as follow: section II summarizes the essential theory for Polynomial Chaos, describes the most common Non-Intrusive methods, and explains the rationale behind the proposed approaches; in section III a brief description is given of the Adjoint techniques, needed to take full advantage of gradient-enhanced Polynomial Chaos and other approaches capable of exploiting derivative information, in real-life applications; section IV describes the test cases as well as the framework employed for addressing them; the results are discussed in section V; the conclusions are drawn in section VI.

II. Polynomial Chaos expansions

Let $(\Theta, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{P})$ be a complete probability space, where Θ is the sample space, \mathcal{F} a σ -algebra containing all the possible outcomes of Θ , and \mathcal{P} a probability measure. It is assumed that the deterministic model which provides the mapping from the uncertain design variables $\mathbf{x} = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^n$ to the scalar QoI, u , the latter expressing the performance of a system, is known. Values taken by the design variables depend on the random event $\vartheta \in \mathcal{F}$, i.e., $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}(\vartheta)$. They can refer to input data, system parameters, or both of them. It is also assumed that u to belong to the $L^2(\mathbb{C})$ space, thus implying finite variance, a condition that holds for the response of most physical systems of interest. Polynomial Chaos expansion (PCE) is a possible way to expand the unknown u in a Fourier-like series. The quantity is projected onto a basis of multivariate orthogonal polynomials $\{\Psi_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ in a set of independent support random variables $\xi(\vartheta) = \{\xi_i(\vartheta)\}_{i=1}^n$ with known probability density functions (PDFs) $w_i(\xi_i)$ and joint PDF $W(\xi)$. u is therefore expressed as a functional. In the remainder of this paper, only independent (uncorrelated) variables will be dealt with. However, this is not always the case, and it may be necessary to represent, for example, spatially-variable inlet conditions in Turbomachinery applications [2, 3] or the viscosity field in a generic fluid flow [4]. A different mathematical tool, namely the (truncated) Karhunen-Loève (KL) expansion [5] is needed to decorrelate the random variables (i.e., to discretize the random field) in a proper and efficient way. More details about the KL expansion and its usage in the context of Polynomial Chaos can be found in [6].

Enforcing the uncertain design variables \mathbf{x} and the random support variables $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ to have the same distribution helps in achieving better convergence behavior of the series to the unknown u [2], but it is not strictly required. In discrete form, a (infinite) Polynomial Chaos expansion can be expressed in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
u(\vartheta) &= c_0 B_0 \\
&+ \sum_{i_1=1}^{\infty} c_{i_1} B_1(\xi_{i_1}(\vartheta)) \\
&+ \sum_{i_1=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i_2=1}^{i_1} c_{i_1 i_2} B_2(\xi_{i_1}(\vartheta), \xi_{i_2}(\vartheta)) \\
&+ \sum_{i_1=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i_2=1}^{i_1} \sum_{i_3=1}^{i_2} c_{i_1 i_2 i_3} B_3(\xi_{i_1}(\vartheta), \xi_{i_2}(\vartheta), \xi_{i_3}(\vartheta)) \\
&+ \dots,
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $\{B_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ are multivariate polynomials involving products of the univariate basis polynomials $\{\psi_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$. The multivariate polynomials multiply deterministic coefficients: they become the only unknowns once a specific realization has been selected among the many made possible by the random event ϑ , and they are unique for that realization. The polynomials form a complete orthogonal basis as they satisfy the orthogonality condition $\langle \Psi_i, \Psi_j \rangle = \delta_{ij}$.

Consider the basis polynomials having a maximum degree p . Their set is then called the p -th Chaos, and the subspace of $L_2(\Theta, \mathcal{P})$ they span takes the name of Polynomial Chaos of order p . A p -th Chaos is then the space of all polynomials $\{\psi_i\}_{i=0}^p$ having degree equal or less than p in all possible combinations of the support random variables. If Hermite polynomials are chosen to construct the basis, the original Homogeneous Chaos [7], often called also Hermite-Chaos or Wiener-Chaos, is found. The expansion given by Eq. 1 converges to u in the L^2 sense for Hermite-Chaos if the ξ_i random variables are Gaussian, following from the Cameron-Martin theorem [8]. Convergence is also achieved for a different choice of the basis, but Hermite polynomials ensure optimal (exponential) convergence rate whenever dealing with normally-distributed variables. For different distributions, optimal convergence can be achieved choosing the family of polynomials from the Askey scheme [9, 10]: this establishes a correspondence between the measure associated with a certain class of orthogonal polynomials (i.e., their weighting function), and the distribution having the same measure as its PDF. The terms gPC (generalized Polynomial Chaos) and Askey-Chaos are often used in literature when referring to this particular choice. Following the Askey scheme ensures the exact representation of a random variable by means of a first-order PC expansion, thus leading to the aforementioned optimality. Note that, according to [10], the Cameron-Martin theorem is expected to be generalized for Askey-Chaos given that the polynomials chosen from the scheme form a complete basis. However, the conditions that make it possible were found only later [11]: they were provided for one-dimensional and finite as well as infinite multi-dimensional bases.

If uncertainties characterizing the system of interest follow distributions other than the ones the Askey scheme accounts for, proper orthogonal polynomials can be constructed numerically, following one of the methods reviewed in [12]. The Stieltjes' procedure [13] constitutes a reliable method: a three-term recurrence relation, holding for all orthogonal polynomials, is employed [1, 2, 14, 15]. The recurrence coefficients are computed with the so-called Christoffel-Darboux formulae; the procedure is stable up to high polynomial degrees, with some limitations [16] that however do not compromise its usability in practical situations. For the sake of generality, in the present work the polynomials were always computed with this method, even when their associated measure match one of the probability density functions covered by the Askey scheme.

The gPC expansion given by Eq. 1 needs to be truncated to a finite number of terms for practical purposes. For convenience, order-based indexing is also replaced with term-based indexing:

$$u(\vartheta) = u(\boldsymbol{\xi}(\vartheta)) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} c_i \Psi_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \approx \sum_{i=0}^P c_i \Psi_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}). \tag{2}$$

Once a proper basis has been chosen, the approximation is known when the c_i coefficients of the expansion are determined. Each multi-dimensional, multivariate basis polynomial can be advantageously expressed as [17]

$$\Psi_j(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \prod_{i=1}^n \psi_{\alpha_i}^{(j)}(\xi_i) = B_n(\xi_{i_1}, \dots, \xi_{i_n}), \quad (3)$$

thus clarifying the relation between Eqs. 1 and 2 and introducing the multi-index $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = \{\alpha_i\}_{i=1}^n$. The variables were requested to be independent ($W(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \prod_{i=1}^n w_i(\xi_i)$). Under these circumstances, a multi-dimensional basis can be obtained as the tensor product of the one-dimensional ones, i.e., $\Psi = \Psi_{\xi_1} \otimes \Psi_{\xi_2} \otimes \dots \otimes \Psi_{\xi_n}$. Due to the tensor product, the number of polynomials to be used for constructing the basis grows exponentially with the number of dimensions (see Tab. 1), and some rule is therefore needed for actual implementations in order to reduce computational efforts. The most common truncation scheme is obtained by fixing a (common) maximum degree p for all the polynomials:

$$(P + 1) = \sum_{s=1}^p \frac{1}{s!} \prod_{r=0}^{s-1} (n + r) + 1 = \binom{n+p}{n} = \frac{(n+p)!}{n!p!}. \quad (4)$$

Appropriate rules can be obtained constraining the multi-index $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ elements to a finite set \mathcal{A} . A few basic examples are given in Tab. 1.

Table 1 Common multi-index sets with the respective rules and cardinalities.

\mathcal{A}		rule	$(P + 1)$
TENSOR PRODUCT SETS	ANISOTROPIC	$\alpha_i \leq p_i$	$\prod_{i=1}^n (p_i + 1)$
	ISOTROPIC	$\alpha_i \leq p$	$(p + 1)^n$
TOTAL ORDER SETS		$ \boldsymbol{\alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \leq p$	$\frac{(p+n)!}{n!p!}$
HYPERBOLIC SETS		$\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^q \right)^{1/q} \leq k, k \in [0.2, 1.0] \approx (k+1)[1 + \log(k+1)]^{n-1}$	

Total order sets, whose cardinality can be computed as in Eq. 4, disregard the higher-order interactions between different dimensions present in tensorized spaces [2, 18], having lesser importance. Other multi-index sets can be advantageously employed for multivariate PCE, but their discussion is beyond the scope of this work: the reader can find further information in [18] and references therein.

A. Computation of PCE coefficients

Polynomial Chaos methods differ for how they compute the coefficients in the expansion. The most general classification distinguishes between Intrusive and Non-Intrusive Polynomial Chaos. The former is strictly related to Stochastic Finite Element methods [19]: model equations are discretized in both the design space and the probability space, and coefficients are computed by means of Galerkin projection. The approach requires the developments of *ad hoc* solvers, making the choice unsuitable for dealing with complex problems for which specialized (deterministic) codes are already available. This is especially true when considering multi-physics applications, which would require an unacceptable effort in order to build from scratch all the simulation routines needed on purpose. On the other side, Non-Intrusive Polynomial Chaos (NIPC) is a class of methods that overcome the need for a new set of (discretized) equations: the response is only known at discrete locations of the probability space and this requires a certain number of deterministic evaluations, so that external solvers can be used as black-boxes. This work only deals with NIPC methods.

1. Spectral projection

The expectation \mathbb{E} induces a measure in the $L^2(\mathbb{C})$ space through the inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$. The norm of an element $h_i(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ of the space is given by

$$\|h_i(\boldsymbol{\xi})\|_{L^2} = \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[h_i^2(\boldsymbol{\xi})]} = \sqrt{\langle h_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}), f_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \rangle}. \quad (5)$$

The inner product can be computed as

$$\langle h_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}), h_j(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \rangle = \int h_i(\boldsymbol{\xi})h_j(\boldsymbol{\xi})W(\boldsymbol{\xi})d\boldsymbol{\xi}. \quad (6)$$

It also follows, from the $L^2(\mathbb{C})$ space properties:

$$\|h_i(\boldsymbol{\xi})\|_{L^2}^2 < \infty \implies \mathbb{E}[h_i(\boldsymbol{\xi})^2] < \infty, \quad (7)$$

i.e., consistently with the fact that $f_i(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ is a second-order random variable, it has finite variance. Finally, the orthogonality constraint requires

$$\langle h_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}), h_j(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \rangle = \langle h_i^2(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \rangle \delta_{ij}, \quad (8)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta. Given these properties, PCE coefficients can be obtained projecting u against each basis element and enforcing orthogonality. Taking the inner product of both the members of Eq. 2:

$$c_i = \frac{\langle u(\boldsymbol{\xi}), \Psi_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \rangle}{\langle \Psi_i^2(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \rangle} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[u(\boldsymbol{\xi})\Psi_i(\boldsymbol{\xi})]}{\mathbb{E}[\Psi_i^2(\boldsymbol{\xi})]} = \frac{1}{\langle \Psi_i^2(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \rangle} \int_{\boldsymbol{\xi}} u(\boldsymbol{\xi})\Psi_i(\boldsymbol{\xi})W(\boldsymbol{\xi})d\boldsymbol{\xi}. \quad (9)$$

Since in Eq. 9 the denominator can be computed analytically, the focus is on finding a proper way of evaluating the numerator.

2. Sampling-based methods

Sampling-based methods directly estimate the expectation in Eq. 9 for each term of the expansion, computing the mean of the products $u(\boldsymbol{\xi})\Psi(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ over a certain number of sampled points within $W(\boldsymbol{\xi})$. A common choice is Monte Carlo Sampling (MCS), which will be used in the following only to validate results obtained with non-sampling methods. MCS is inefficient in consequence of the poor rate of convergence of the expansion. In general, convergence of the statistics scales with the inverse of the square root of the number of points. Some advantage is offered with regard to problem dimensionality: convergence properties of MCS are independent of the number of dimensions involved. This feature, together with the certain asymptotic convergence, makes MCS a suitable choice for providing reference values with which other methods can be validated. Potentially more efficient sampling techniques, like Quasi-Monte Carlo sampling (QMC), Latin Hypercube sampling (LHS), and especially Hammersley sampling (HS) [20], are also available, but they are still too expensive for many practical applications and preferably employed, again, for validation purposes [21].

3. Quadrature-based (Collocation) methods

A different approach consists in numerically computing the integral in Eq. 9 by means of quadrature rules. A generic one-dimensional quadrature rule is formulated as

$$\int_{\boldsymbol{\xi}} h(\boldsymbol{\xi})d\boldsymbol{\xi} \approx \mathcal{U} h(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i h(\boldsymbol{\xi}^{(i)}). \quad (10)$$

Gaussian quadrature is assumed, i.e., evaluations of f are performed at the $\{\boldsymbol{\xi}^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^m$ collocation points that are zeros for the orthogonal polynomial of order m , with weights $\{w_i\}_{i=1}^m$. The n -dimensional quadrature is then obtained as the tensor product of an equal number of one-dimensional quadratures:

$$\mathcal{Q}h(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{\alpha_1=1}^{m_1} \cdots \sum_{\alpha_n=1}^{m_n} h(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{\alpha_1}, \dots, \boldsymbol{\xi}_{\alpha_n}) \prod_{k=1}^n \gamma_{n_k} = (\mathcal{U}^{\alpha_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes \mathcal{U}^{\alpha_n}) = \bigotimes_{j=1}^n \mathcal{U}^{\alpha_j}. \quad (11)$$

A full-tensor quadrature, or full-factorial numerical integration (FFNI) defined by Eq. 11 is only suitable for a small number of dimensions. In order to alleviate the *curse of dimensionality* [22], a construction due to Smolyak [23] and leading to sparse quadrature, or sparse grid numerical integration (SGNI), can be advantageously exploited in

presence of a moderately large number of dimensions [24]. The general isotropic Smolyak's multi-dimensional sparse quadrature rule can be written as [25]

$$\mathcal{S}(l, n) = \underbrace{\sum_{l+1 \leq |\alpha| \leq l+n}}_{\text{Admissible multi-indexes}} \underbrace{(-1)^{l+n-|\alpha|} \binom{n-1}{l+n-|\alpha|}}_{\text{Counting coefficient}} \underbrace{\bigotimes_{j=1}^n \mathcal{U}^{\alpha_j}}_{\text{Full-tensor rule}}. \quad (12)$$

For a given level l , the number of abscissas used by the corresponding one-dimensional rules is governed by a growth rule, determining how the multi-index increases with the order of the rule. A common choice for Gaussian quadratures is to employ linear growth. In general, the number of evaluations of the system response for sparse quadratures scales better with regard to the number of dimensions, in consequence of the fact the full-tensor quadrature is replaced by a linear combinations of lower-order quadrature rules. Preference over tensor-product quadratures is reasonable for $n > 4$, whereas for a lower dimensionality sparse quadratures are more expensive. Several variants of the classical construction by Smolyak [23] are reviewed in [26].

4. Least Squares Approximation

Differently from projection-based methods, whose target is the approximation of either the expectations or the integrals in Eq. 9, regression-based methods aim at building a surrogate model of the PCE. Expansion of the QoI given by Eq. 2 depends on ξ , whose coordinates are in general a consequence of the random event ϑ . In short, the QoI assumes a different value for every realization or outcome, which dictates the (deterministic) coefficients - being the PCE basis unique once ξ and some rule for the truncation are given. If $(N_s + 1)$ training points are chosen from the joint density $W(\xi)$, the actual PCE coefficients can be approximated searching for the $\{\hat{c}\}_{i=0}^{N_s}$ values that best reproduce the outcomes at the same points, i.e., solving for the system

$$\begin{pmatrix} \Psi_0(\xi^{(0)}) & \Psi_1(\xi^{(0)}) & \dots & \Psi_P(\xi^{(0)}) \\ \Psi_0(\xi^{(1)}) & \Psi_1(\xi^{(1)}) & \dots & \Psi_P(\xi^{(1)}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \Psi_0(\xi^{(N_s)}) & \Psi_1(\xi^{(N_s)}) & \dots & \Psi_P(\xi^{(N_s)}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{c}_0 \\ \hat{c}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \hat{c}_{N_s} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} u(\xi^{(0)}) \\ u(\xi^{(1)}) \\ \vdots \\ u(\xi^{(N_s)}) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

The system can be expressed in compact form as $\underline{\Psi} \hat{c} = \mathbf{u}$. Different regression-based methods result from the choice of different algorithms for computing its solution. Two common choices in the context of Polynomial Chaos are ℓ_1 -minimization [27–30] and ℓ_2 -minimization, better known as Least Squares [3, 18, 20, 31–35]. As for their applications outside the UQ area, they are associated with the solution of under-determined and over-determined systems, respectively.

Ordinary Least Squares, i.e., linear regression, leads to a solution of the system 13 in the form

$$\hat{c} = \left(\underline{\Psi}^T \underline{\Psi} \right)^{-1} \underline{\Psi}^T \mathbf{u}. \quad (14)$$

A Least Squares surrogate for the PCE of a QoI can be also called its Least Squares Approximation (LSA), and it is similar, in a statistical sense, to the regression of the exact solution u in the PC basis [35, 36].

5. Oversampling

Employing Least Squares, system 13 requires a number of equations - and the same number of training points for the surrogate -, equal at least to the number of elements in the PCE basis, for the stability constraints over condition of the matrix; full rank must also be ensured. In general, the system will be overdetermined. Calling oversampling the ratio of the actual number of equations to the minimum and denote it with ζ , the overall cost of the expansion will be $\propto \zeta \frac{(n+p)!}{n!p!}$, assuming a total-order set for the basis (Tab. 1). Therefore, large oversampling levels cancel out the computational advantage against Collocation methods to some extent. In literature, a value $\zeta = 2$ is sometimes regarded as optimal [20, 34] for limiting errors to a negligible value. In [32], linear scaling (with respect to cardinality of the gPC basis) by a factor in the range [1.5, 2.0] is reported to be acceptable as a rule of thumb, but the asymptotic need for quadratic scaling is recognized for applications limited to lower-order (up to the third) expansions; they successfully applied a sub-linear scaling randomly sub-sampling from the tensor product point set of Gaussian quadrature points.

Much depends on the particular implementation and choice of the points: an universal value ensuring stability and accuracy cannot be established once and for all either for specific (sub)sampling choices or the general case. Moreover, determining the optimal value is not a simple task and requires consideration of different metrics, since there are cases involving low condition numbers but significant aliasing errors, see for example the analyses in [37]. An *ad hoc* study for the implementation used in this work is outside the scope of the present paper. All the results that are presented were obtained with an oversampling level chosen on the basis of *a posteriori* assessments. The choice will be motivated, showing as for the present implementation large oversampling factors give currently no clear advantages. A fair distance from the unitary value has however been ensured so to avoid numerical instabilities. The partial independence from oversampling leads to advantages and disadvantages. The removal of such a problematic constraint as the need to scale the factor with the number of dimensions or the order of the expansion is surely a benefit. On the other side, oversampling cannot be used for significantly increase accuracy of a Least Squares surrogate without increasing the expansion order, which in turn means an increase in the number of training points according to the total order set. In the following section, this problem is addressed from the opposite perspective: instead of maximizing the accuracy of an n -th order LSA, its cost is minimized instead. Doing so, the foundation for combining LSA and Adjoint techniques is also laid.

6. Gradient-enhanced Polynomial Chaos

Over the last decade a growing attention has been paid to the so called gradient-enhanced Polynomial Chaos methods, sometimes referred to as Polynomial Regression with Derivative information (PRD) [38, 39]. In a nutshell, a gPC expansion can be obtained with comparable level of accuracy but significantly fewer sampling points if we local information (otherwise limited to point evaluations of u) is integrated by the derivatives of u . The discussion will be limited to Least Squares surrogates, but in the context of regression-based PCE the idea was previously (and successfully) applied to l_1 -minimization (compressed sensing) [29, 30, 40], whereas parallels in the area of Kriging methods can be found in [41–43]. Previous applications to Least Squares surrogates are discussed in [38, 39, 44].

For LSA, inclusion of derivative information is straightforward, and fully effective. Since all it is needed for computing the expansion is to build a linear system which is not underdetermined, the number of sub-sampled points can be reduced simply writing a number of additional equations so to achieve full rank. For the k -th point:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi_j}(\xi^{(k)}) = \sum_{i=0}^{N_s} c_i \frac{\partial \Psi_i}{\partial \xi_j}(\xi^{(k)}). \quad (15)$$

If N_s is the number of points required for the surrogate model, the system in Eq. 13 becomes

$$\begin{pmatrix}
\Psi_0(\xi^{(0)}) & \Psi_1(\xi^{(0)}) & \dots & \Psi_P(\xi^{(0)}) \\
\Psi_0(\xi^{(1)}) & \Psi_1(\xi^{(1)}) & \dots & \Psi_P(\xi^{(1)}) \\
\vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\
\Psi_0(\xi^{(N_s)}) & \Psi_1(\xi^{(N_s)}) & \dots & \Psi_P(\xi^{(N_s)}) \\
\partial_0 \Psi_0(\xi^{(0)}) & \partial_0 \Psi_1(\xi^{(0)}) & \dots & \partial_0 \Psi_P(\xi^{(0)}) \\
\partial_1 \Psi_0(\xi^{(0)}) & \partial_1 \Psi_1(\xi^{(0)}) & \dots & \partial_1 \Psi_P(\xi^{(0)}) \\
\vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\
\partial_n \Psi_0(\xi^{(0)}) & \partial_n \Psi_1(\xi^{(0)}) & \dots & \partial_n \Psi_P(\xi^{(0)}) \\
\partial_0 \Psi_0(\xi^{(1)}) & \partial_0 \Psi_1(\xi^{(1)}) & \dots & \partial_0 \Psi_P(\xi^{(1)}) \\
\partial_1 \Psi_0(\xi^{(1)}) & \partial_1 \Psi_1(\xi^{(1)}) & \dots & \partial_1 \Psi_P(\xi^{(1)}) \\
\vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\
\partial_n \Psi_0(\xi^{(1)}) & \partial_n \Psi_1(\xi^{(1)}) & \dots & \partial_n \Psi_P(\xi^{(1)}) \\
\vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\
\partial_0 \Psi_0(\xi^{(N_s)}) & \partial_0 \Psi_1(\xi^{(N_s)}) & \dots & \partial_0 \Psi_P(\xi^{(N_s)}) \\
\partial_1 \Psi_0(\xi^{(N_s)}) & \partial_1 \Psi_1(\xi^{(N_s)}) & \dots & \partial_1 \Psi_P(\xi^{(N_s)}) \\
\vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\
\partial_n \Psi_0(\xi^{(N_s)}) & \partial_n \Psi_1(\xi^{(N_s)}) & \dots & \partial_n \Psi_P(\xi^{(N_s)})
\end{pmatrix}
\begin{pmatrix}
\hat{c}_0 \\
\hat{c}_1 \\
\vdots \\
\hat{c}_{N_s}
\end{pmatrix}
=
\begin{pmatrix}
u(\xi^{(0)}) \\
u(\xi^{(1)}) \\
\vdots \\
u(\xi^{(N_s)}) \\
\partial_0 u(\xi^{(0)}) \\
\partial_1 u(\xi^{(0)}) \\
\vdots \\
\partial_n u(\xi^{(0)}) \\
\partial_0 u(\xi^{(1)}) \\
\partial_1 u(\xi^{(1)}) \\
\vdots \\
\partial_n u(\xi^{(1)}) \\
\vdots \\
\partial_0 u(\xi^{(N_s)}) \\
\partial_1 u(\xi^{(N_s)}) \\
\vdots \\
\partial_n u(\xi^{(N_s)})
\end{pmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

n more equations become available for every point. The ratio between the number of points without and with gradient enhancing is then

$$\frac{P+1}{N_s+1} \simeq n+1, \quad (17)$$

regardless of the expansion order. An overdetermined system is always needed in practice and then $(P+1)$ will be increased by ζ times, where ζ is the oversampling factor, eventually resulting in

$$N_s+1 \simeq \zeta \frac{P+1}{n+1} = \zeta \frac{(p+n)!}{(n+1)!p!}. \quad (18)$$

Second derivative information could also be provided following the same logic, but here only solutions that make possible the combination with usual Adjoint techniques will be considered. Second-order Adjoint approaches giving the Hessian have already been formulated [45] and applied in different fields including air traffic control [46] and aerodynamic shape optimization in a deterministic context [47]. Applications to UQ and global sensitivity analysis, as an alternative to gradient-enhanced linear regressions, have also been proposed for distributed parameter models.

With Collocation methods there is the need to saturate basis cardinality with the tensor- or sparse-grid points, but derivative information can be provided in order to improve accuracy of moment sensitivities (see Sec. II.C). Since derivative information is not available for also improving the moments through more accurate expansions, in this case the definition of gradient-enhanced PCE does not apply. The advantage is still valuable.

7. Choice of (sub-)sampled points

Whereas for quadrature-based methods a point arrangement is fixed around the nominal points in the design space, Least Squares do not impose any restriction, similarly to other regression-based methods. For LSAs, any set of points is equally good as long as it provides fair coverage of the design space and minimizes the condition number for the linear system 13 or 16, which has an impact on the stability of the solution algorithm. When weighted Least Squares are employed, not only points, but also weights have to be chosen according to some rationale.

For a given order p of the polynomial basis, and assuming an oversampling level large enough to have a negligible influence on the matrix condition, accuracy of Least Squares surrogate essentially depends on the choice of sampling points, i.e., on their distribution in the space spanned by ξ . In general, the choice implies the selection of a sampling

Fig. 1 Evaluation points for 3-rd order bases. Normalized Gaussian distribution.

strategy and a suitable method for (eventually) sub-sampling from the main set, ordinarily involving the formulation of an optimization problem [37]. Sampling techniques can fall into three several categories: different strategies involving both random and deterministic sampling are discussed in [35] and references therein. The aim is to minimize the number of points required for a stable solution and for the convergence to the best approximation of the coefficients. If random sampling is employed, stability and accuracy are possible for a number of points that grows with the square of the polynomial space ([33] and references therein). They can be achieved for a more affordable number of points - scaling linear with the cardinality of the polynomial space -, if such points are sub-sampled from full-tensor Gaussian quadrature points [32]. The linear rather than quadratic scaling makes possible to generate stable high-order Least Squares surrogates with acceptable oversampling rates. The latter result motivated the approach originally proposed in [18] and applied to turbomachinery in [3]: sub-sampling from the quadrature points is assisted by QR factorization with column pivoting in order to select a proper subset having the same cardinality as the PC space, deterministically. The method has not been extended to gradient-enhanced surrogates yet. In the present work, a set of Gaussian points is randomly selected from tensor-product grids without performing an explicit optimization. Quadrature points having order $(p + 1)$ are employed when building a standard LSA. Fig. 1 gives an example of the points used by FFNI, SGNI and LSA for the same PCE order and numbers of variables.

For gradient-enhanced surrogates, the choice was made to sub-sample from Gaussian points of reduced order. For any number n of variables, the order p_q of the quadrature points is set to $\text{round}(p/2)$, where round denotes rounding up. The number N_q of available point for sub-sampling then equals $(p_q + 1)^n$, following from Tab. 1. Such a choice always ensures for the set of the available points a cardinality equal or larger than the total-order set. Bounds are applied, however, to the maximum oversampling rates achievable. In particular, in the special case of a one-dimensional problem, the oversampling ζ can be lower than 1.5: for $p = 10$, for instance, N_q equals the number of points prescribed by the total-order index set, so no oversampling can be applied. This drawback was accepted because the implementation of the gradient-enhanced Least Squares surrogates was mainly aimed at dealing with problems having a higher dimensionality; for such a low number of variables, expensiveness of a standard LSA can be considered affordable, in any case. Starting from $p = 2$, enough points are available so to ensure $\max \zeta \geq 1.5$ for any dimensionality, at any expansion order (Fig. 2. For increasing n values, cardinality grows more rapidly for the

Fig. 2 Available oversampling levels for different numbers of variables and different expansion orders when employing gradient-enhanced LSA surrogate.

reduced-order tensor sets than the total-order sets, hence the bounds on the oversampling level become not meaningful. At the same time, employing reduced-order tensor grids allows for a better control over the (still random) selection of the points. Since the gradient-enhanced surrogates require a significantly lower number of points, there is a higher risk of extracting a problematic set from the grid with regards to the distribution of the points - e.g., having all the points aligned along the same direction, or clustered in a small region of $W(\xi)$ asymmetric with respect to the null vector $\xi = \mathbf{0}$ -, especially for low-order expansions. Sub-sampling from full-order tensor grids, reduced-order tensor grids and sparse grids is shown in Fig. 3. It should be noted that inclusion of the point corresponding to the null vector is enforced - the choice is extended to non-enhanced surrogates. This is enough to make the selection of Fig. 3b better than those in Figs. 3a and 3c: the probability for the points to span both the directions becomes 1, whereas otherwise it would be $2/3$. For the tensor grid of the second order, the probability is $1/2$. Note that given the low dimensionality, a sparse grid has more points than the tensor grid of the same order, and then sub-sampling from it would lead to even worse results.

B. Computation of moments

An advantage of PCE is given by the fact that moments can be obtained with no significant efforts after the expansion coefficients have been computed. The mean only requires knowledge of the first PC coefficient:

$$\mu = \mathbb{E}[u] = \int_{\xi} \Psi(\xi) W(\xi) d\xi = c_0. \quad (19)$$

The standard deviation can be computed as

$$\sigma^2 = \mathbb{E}[(u - \mathbb{E}[u])^2] = \int_{\xi} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^p c_i \Psi_i(\xi) \right\}^2 W(\xi) d\xi = \sum_{i=1}^p c_i^2 \langle \Psi_i^2 \rangle, \quad (20)$$

where $\langle \Psi_i^2 \rangle$ are known [19] or can be retrieved numerically without requiring expensive computations.

Fig. 3 Effects of different random sub-sampling choices for two-dimensional gradient-enhanced Least Squares surrogates. Normalized Gaussian distribution.

C. Moments' sensitivities

This work focuses on local (moment) sensitivity analysis: the interest is on evaluating gradients of the QoI's moments at prescribed points, as they represent the directions of more robust designs. In UQ, moment sensitivities are used to identify the design variables having the largest impact on the QoI's value; if a variable produces large deviations by the QoI, it negatively affects robustness of the design. In RO, moment sensitivities can be used in the optimization process when gradient-based algorithms are employed: objective and constraints can be formulated as linear combinations of the moments (see Sec. IV.B), and consequently their gradients are linear combinations of the moment sensitivities. After optimization, function sensitivities, i.e., derivatives of the QoI with respect to the design variables, can still be an important factor in assessing the feasibility of the optimized design: although optimal, a design presenting large variations of the QoI with regards to small changes in the design variables could still be considered inadequate.

Different methodologies have been used for computing the moments' gradients:

- 1) The basic approach to approximate the moments' derivative is by means of finite differences. Whereas in theory different levels of accuracy can be achieved by using different stencils, the most common approximations are one-sided and centred differences, respectively first- and second-order accurate. Referring, for instance, to the mean value, the derivative for the i -th variable can be approximated as:

$$\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial \xi_i} \approx \frac{\mu(\xi_i + \varepsilon) - \mu(\xi_i)}{\varepsilon} \quad (21)$$

if employing one-sided differences and

$$\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial \xi_i} \approx \frac{\mu(\xi_i + \varepsilon) - \mu(\xi_i - \varepsilon)}{2\varepsilon} \quad (22)$$

for two-sided differences, where ε is a fixed, discrete interval assumed constant for all variables. The suffixes FD1 and FD2 will be appended to the acronyms FFNI and SGNI when moment sensitivities for quadrature-based methods are computed by means one-sided and two-sided finite differences, respectively. A constant discretization interval $\varepsilon = 0.01$ is used based on the results of preliminary tests to accommodate all the cases presented in this paper.

- 2) An alternative approach to calculate the moments' gradient is by means of the functional representation of the function gradient. The PCE for the function gradient, similarly to Eq. 2, takes the form:

$$\nabla u \approx \sum_{i=0}^P \nabla c_i \Psi_i(\xi) = \sum_{i=0}^P g_i \Psi_i(\xi). \quad (23)$$

Following from Eq. 19, sensitivities of the mean value can then be obtained as

$$\nabla \mu = \nabla c_0 = g_0, \quad (24)$$

and, for the variance, similarly to Eq. 20:

$$\nabla \sigma^2 \approx \sum_{i=1}^P \nabla c_i^2 \langle \Psi_i^2 \rangle. \quad (25)$$

The derivatives of the standard deviation can be obtained recalling the derivation of a product of functions, and rearranging:

$$\nabla \sigma \approx \frac{1}{\sigma} \sum_{i=1}^P c_i \nabla c_i \langle \Psi_i^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{\sigma} \sum_{i=1}^P c_i g_i \langle \Psi_i^2 \rangle. \quad (26)$$

The gradients of the function at quadrature points can be available thank to the availability of an Adjoint solver (as in [48]), or can be provided by a (higher-order) PCE. The acronyms FFNI-G, SGNI-G, LSA2-G will be used for identifying the use of tensor-product quadratures, sparse quadratures, and Least Square Approximations, respectively, in conjunction with Adjoint information for computing moment sensitivities. The "G" indicates that the QoI's gradient is provided by external routines to the code responsible for UQ and RO. If the gradient information required in Eqs. 24 and 26 is provided by a PCE approximation of the function, the base acronyms

Table 2 Summary of different methods for computing moments’ sensitivities. Note: for algebraic models, Adjoint is substituted by direct evaluations (exact derivatives are retrieved employing computer algebra).

APPROACH	COMPUTATION OF PCE COEFFICIENTS	MOMENTS’ GRADIENT METHOD	QoI’s GRADIENT EVALUATION	
			SOURCE	USE
FFNI	Full-factorial numerical integration	Eqs. 24 and 26	QoI’s PCE	Moments’ sensitivities
SGNI	Sparse-grid numerical integration	Eqs. 24 and 26	QoI’s PCE	Moments’ sensitivities
LSA	Least Squares approximation	Eq. 22	–	(Not required)
LSA2	Least Squares approximation (variant)	Eqs. 24 and 26	QoI’s PCE	Moments’ sensitivities
FFNI-G	Full-factorial numerical integration	Eqs. 24 and 26	Adjoint	Moments’ sensitivities
SGNI-G	Sparse-grid numerical integration	Eqs. 24 and 26	Adjoint	Moments’ sensitivities
LSA-G	Least Squares approximation	Eq. 22	Adjoint	Gradient-enhanced LSA (Eq. 16)
LSA2-G	Least Squares approximation (variant)	Eqs. 24 and 26	Adjoint	Moments’ sensitivities
FFNI-FD1/FD2	Full-factorial numerical integration	Eqs. 21 and 22	–	(Not required)
SGNI-FD1/FD2	Sparse-grid numerical integration	Eqs. 21 and 22	–	(Not required)

FFNI, SGNI and LSA2 will be used, indicating that no external information is provided except for the function evaluations.

- 3) When employing Least Squares surrogates, moment sensitivities can be computed by means of finite differences even without requiring additional deterministic evaluations. The evaluations of the moments at the additional stencil points in Eqs. 21 and 22 can be performed with the same deterministic evaluations used for the base points: only the values of the orthogonal polynomials will change, therefore affecting the values of the expansion’s coefficients. Since the number of evaluations is not increased, two-sided differences can be advantageously employed without significantly affecting the efficiency of the method. In the following, LSA will refer to Least Squares surrogates for which the moment sensitivities are obtained with this method; LSA-G will denote the gradient-enhanced variant.

The different approaches used in this work are summarized in Tab. 2.

D. Reuse of points

As discussed, Least Squares surrogates allow for significant reductions in the number of evaluations, and computational efforts are not going to significantly increase if a proper strategy is employed for computing local sensitivities. However, there is still room for improvement when performing optimization: there are chances for an optimizer, while exploring the design space, to go through points very near each other or even, depending on how good the optimizer is, to reach a same point more than once. Referring to gradient-based algorithms, situations like the direction reversal that can occur after too long steps towards one of the boundaries imposed by the constraints, or the twisted trajectories that can take place around local optima, may be taken as examples. Saving a history with all the nominal points explored by the optimizer and the results there computed is enough for avoiding redundant calculations. But what about evaluation points used for computing expansions around very similar, though different nominal points? If computing quadrature-based expansions, evaluations can be reused only for points that exactly match. On the other side, use of surrogates allows for a relatively free choice of the point positions, and therefore replacing a point with another one that is near enough can be considered acceptable. Here, exploit the nature of surrogate-based expansions is exploited so to avoid the occurrence of ineffective (and expensive) evaluations at points that can be considered as repetitions except for a small tolerance. Overloading the notation, such tolerance will be named ε and its value will be set to 10^{-6} for all cases. This way, an even greater computational efficiency is obtained with the Least Squares approach, while a history for the nominal points explored by the optimizer is still enforced for all methods, so to overcome the limitations of the chosen optimizer and making efficiency partially independent from that choice. For algebraic optimization test cases, reuse of points will be always employed. For the real-life test case, results will be presented for computations performed with and without reuse. The acronyms LSA-R and LSA-GR will be used in the latter case if points are reused, for distinguishing them from LSA and LSA-G. The approach is not extended to LSA2 and LSA2-G.

III. Adjoint approach for design sensitivities

For algebraic problems, gradients of the QoIs with respect to the design variables can be obtained without significant efforts. When demanding simulations are needed, Adjoint techniques [49] can be exploited. They allow computation

of the gradient (function sensitivities) at a cost comparable to that of a single deterministic run. The underlying key concept is straightforward to understand: given a functional depending on the solution of a mathematical model, some conditions can be associated, i.e., for the cases of concern, the model equations are required to hold; at this point, either the point of view of optimal control theory (formulation of the dual problem [50]), or that of minimization problems in terms of Lagrangian multipliers [51], can be taken. Both ways lead us to write a set of equations (Adjoint equations), whose variables are called Adjoint variables: with respect to the two approaches, they correspond to dual variables and Lagrangian multipliers, at the same time. Solving for the adjoint variables implies knowledge of the gradients. Adjoint techniques can belong to two different families: in continuous Adjoint, the Adjoint equations are derived from the exact model equation and then discretized, whereas in discrete adjoint they are derived from the discretized model equations. A comparison of the two in the context of design optimization can be found, e.g., in [52]. In the following, reference will be made exclusively to discrete Adjoint. In the past, discrete Adjoint was burdened with some serious limitations, due to the need to employ exact linearization of the discretized model equations, whose coding is nontrivial especially when higher-order discretization schemes are in use. Today, algorithmic differentiation (AD) significantly helps in overcoming the problem.

Let \mathbf{U} be the vector of the variables from which the deterministic model depends, $R(\mathbf{U}; \mathbf{x})$ the residuals of the linearized (discretized) equations having the design variables $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^n$ as parameters - it is assumed that the system generated by the discretized equations needs to be solved iteratively -, and \mathcal{I} an objective function. The aim is to obtain the derivatives of a deterministic function - be it the objective or, eventually, one of the constraints - with respect to the design variables, i.e.,

$$\frac{d\mathcal{I}}{d\mathbf{x}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{I}}{\partial \mathbf{U}} \frac{d\mathbf{U}}{d\mathbf{x}} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{I}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}. \quad (27)$$

Starting from a given point in the design space, were the derivatives computed by means, e.g., of finite differences, at least n additional evaluations of \mathcal{I} would be needed, i.e., no less than $n(P + 1)$ additional time-consuming runs of the employed deterministic solver. The number could increase of an order of magnitude or worse during exploration of the design space by an optimizer. Given the availability of a good solver and the use of proper convergence criteria for deterministic flow solutions, one can write

$$R(\mathbf{U}; \mathbf{x}) \approx 0 \implies \frac{dR}{d\mathbf{x}} = \frac{\partial R}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \frac{d\mathbf{U}}{d\mathbf{x}} + \frac{\partial R}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \approx 0. \quad (28)$$

Enforcing the approximation to be an equality, then follows

$$\frac{d\mathbf{U}}{d\mathbf{x}} = - \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial \mathbf{U}} \right)^{-1} \frac{\partial R}{\partial \mathbf{x}} = \boldsymbol{\lambda}^T, \quad (29)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ is the vector containing the adjoint variables. Solving the Adjoint equations

$$\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial \mathbf{U}} \right)^T \boldsymbol{\lambda} = - \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{I}}{\partial \mathbf{U}} \right) \quad (30)$$

values of the Adjoint variables given by the solution $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ can be used to compute function sensitivities as

$$\frac{d\mathcal{I}}{d\mathbf{x}} = \boldsymbol{\lambda}^T \frac{\partial R}{\partial \mathbf{x}} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{I}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}. \quad (31)$$

Instead of solving $n(P + 1)$ times governing equations of the model, the system given by Eq. 30 is solved just once, thus requires approximately the same time needed for obtaining a single model solution. Computation of function sensitivities through Eq. 31, in comparison, presents a negligible cost, only requiring dot products.

IV. Methodology

In order to show advantages and weaknesses of the discussed approaches, some test cases are addressed employing an in-house framework. At the heart of the framework reside the computational routines aimed at computing the PCE expansions, which owe much to the Effective Quadrature library [53]: a significant part of the code base devoted to UQ can be considered a fork of this project, and the original contribution in terms of development of the methods could eventually go upstream or help in extending the current capabilities of the library. Because of this connection, most of the code is currently written in Python language, although a more efficient implementations in a compiled language

such as, for instance, C++, is planned for the future, at least for the computational core. Among the most known libraries extensively used for building the framework there are NumPy [54], SymPy [55] and SciPy [56]. Efforts have been made to stitch the different framework components around a common interface: computer algebra simplifies function definitions for the user and supports extensibility of the built-in library of algebraic benchmarks; data exchange layers for external deterministic solvers can be easily added without requiring modifications to the main code; outputs follow a common template regardless of the external codes involved, and post-processing routines allow for different analyses according to the requested task (uncertainty quantification or robust optimization) - most of the figures and tables (in L^AT_EX format) presented in this paper were obtained directly from such routines.

A. Algebraic UQ cases

Three UQ cases were chosen in order to test the accuracy and efficiency of the different approaches for the computation of moment sensitivities, and to show the clear advantages of Least Squares surrogates against quadrature-based methods. All the approaches are validated by comparison of their results with reference values obtained with bootstrap resampling [57, 58]: 500 bootstrap samples with 10^4 observations were randomly extracted from the Monte Carlo simulations for each test case, following the approach used in [36]. If standard MCS is employed for validation purposes, several runs employing equally numerous samples are required in order to overcome the random nature of the method. Also, fundamental statistics can be computed but their confidence intervals cannot, since the distribution followed by the population is not known in advance. Bootstrap allows resampling with repetition from the same sample, which is treated as the population itself. Random construction of bootstrap samples ensures that final statistics are always computed with regards to a Gaussian distribution, and therefore confidence intervals can be effectively estimated no matter the distribution of the original (unknown) population. Estimates on the population distribution moments are also expected to provide better accuracy for the same computational effort, making bootstrap more efficient than standard MCS. An oversampling level $\zeta = 1.5$ is employed for all Least Squares surrogates unless otherwise specified. FFNI and FFNI-G will be only employed for the case involving the lesser dimensionality.

1. Ishigami

The Ishigami function, originally formulated in [59], is often employed as a benchmark for UQ codes [21, 60–63]. The function has expression

$$\sin(x_1) + a \sin^2(x_2) + b x_3^4 \sin(x_1), \quad (32)$$

where $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^3 \sim U[-\pi, \pi]$, $a = 7$ and $b = 0.1$. Exact values for the moments are given by

$$\begin{cases} \mu = \frac{a}{2} \\ \sigma^2 = \frac{a^2}{8} + \frac{b\pi^4}{5} + \frac{b^2\pi^8}{18} + \frac{1}{2} \end{cases} . \quad (33)$$

The benchmark is usually employed in the context of global sensitivity analysis, since Sobol indexes are also known algebraically. However, there is no reason not to extend its applicability to local sensitivity analysis: not only the function is challenging due to the strong non-linearity, which requires high-order PCEs to properly estimate the moments; but being the moments constant, accuracy in computation of their derivatives can be put to test as well: the fact that only zeros are expected does not mean that they are simple to obtain. This test case will also help in providing some sensibility for judgment of the reference values computed with bootstrap: the confidence intervals give an idea of how large can be the distance between their bounds and the exact values.

2. UQ1

An *ad hoc* test case presenting not as a strong non-linearity as the Ishigami function, but a quite larger number of variables, is now introduced. Without imagination, name UQ1 was chosen for the function, whose expression is

$$\frac{x_1^3 + (x_1 + x_2)^2 + x_3 x_4 x_5}{(x_6 + x_7 + x_8)(x_9 + x_{10})} \quad (34)$$

Choice of distributions for the random input is of no particular concern, since the methods to be compared are expected to perform equally well regardless of the polynomials used for the bases - the polynomials are always computed

numerically, even if different choices are available for the ones belonging to the Askey scheme. For this test case, only normally-distributed variables are therefore assumed:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &\sim N(2, 1) & x_2 &\sim N(1, 1) & x_3 &\sim N(3, 1) & x_4 &\sim N(2, 2) & x_5 &\sim N(4, 2) \\ x_6 &\sim N(7, 2) & x_7 &\sim N(10, 3) & x_8 &\sim N(4, 1) & x_9 &\sim N(5, 1) & x_{10} &\sim N(6, 1) \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

3. UQ2

The last UQ test case, UQ2, trades three variables for a relatively higher non-linearity, leading to the need for 6-th order expansions. The function is formulated as

$$x_1 \cos(x_2) + 0.01(x_1 x_2 x_3 x_4 x_5) + x_4 \log(x_5), \quad (36)$$

where the uncertain variables are again normally distributed:

$$x_1 \sim N(2, 1) \quad x_2 \sim N(1, 1) \quad x_3 \sim N(3, 1) \quad x_4 \sim N(2, 2) \quad x_5 \sim N(10, 2). \quad (37)$$

B. Algebraic optimization cases

The SciPy library gives access to several optimization algorithms. Without limiting the code to such choice, a [64] wrapper to the well worked Fortran implementation of the SLSQP (Sequential Least Squares Quadratic Programming) algorithm [65] was employed. The algorithm provides a robust solution for non-linearly constrained, gradient-based optimization.

As a candidate function for basing the RO cases upon, the Rosenbrock function [66] was chosen. It is usually proposed as a benchmark for optimization algorithms [67–69], but its employment has been extended several times to UQ and RO [17, 70–72]. The base function has expression:

$$f(x_1, x_2) = c(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (x_1 - 1)^2, \quad (38)$$

where c is a constant whose value will be assumed to be always 100 in the following. The function can be easily generalized to an arbitrary number of variables, i.e.:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} [100(x_{i+1} - x_i)^2 + (x_i - 1)^2]. \quad (39)$$

Three different cases was tailored on the Rosenbrock function. Two cases involving the standard function, first without and then with constraints applied, are firstly presented. The generalization of the function to five variables is then addressed for unconstrained optimization. The variables are assumed to be normally distributed with unitary variance and constrain their domain to $\{x_i \in [-2.048, 2.048]\}_{i=1}^n$. The points $\mathbf{x}_0 = [1, 1]$ and $\mathbf{x}_0 = [2, \dots, 2]$ are used as starting points for both deterministic and robust optimization for the standard (two-dimensional) and generalized Rosenbrock functions, respectively. All the algebraic optimization cases are addressed with fourth-order expansions, high enough to ensure that the prescribed order is not a limiting factor itself with regards to accuracy. For each case, robust optimization is performed employing the same Polynomial Chaos approaches used for UQ. Deterministic optimization is also performed for comparison, for the generalized Rosenbrock case: in order to show the lesser robustness of deterministic optima and how it evolves during optimization, UQ is performed at each iteration. The moments are computed employing FFNI-G if a low dimensionality is involved, SGNI-G otherwise. In contrast with deterministic optimization, robust optimization takes into account the impact of design uncertainties on the QoIs, which become stochastic, i.e., they can be described with their probability density function or with their moments. Note that since $\mathbf{x}_0 = [1, 1]$ is the optimal point for the two-dimensional deterministic problems, only RO is actually performed for the standard Rosenbrock function, in both the unconstrained and the constrained case: the initial point is already the optimum, but its lesser robustness with regards to the optima given by robust optimization is shown. As for UQ cases, an oversampling level $\zeta = 1.5$ is employed for all Least Squares surrogates unless otherwise specified.

In a RO, the objective becomes the minimization of the moments of one or more QoIs, subject to some constraints on the moments of other quantities. To avoid an excessive increase of the problem complexity, the objectives and constraints can be reformulated as a weighted sum of the lower order moments. A DO problem can be formulated as

$$\begin{cases} \min & f_i(\mathbf{x}) & \text{for } i = 1, \dots, I \\ \text{s.t.} & g_j(\mathbf{x}) & \text{for } j = 1, \dots, J \\ & x_n \in [l_n, u_n] & \text{for } n = 1, \dots, N \end{cases} \quad (40)$$

whereas a RO problem takes the form

$$\begin{cases} \min & \mu_{f_i}(\mathbf{x}) + k_i^o \sigma_{f_i}(\mathbf{x}) & \text{for } i = 1, \dots, I \\ \text{s.t.} & \mu_{g_j}(\mathbf{x}) + k_j^c \sigma_{g_j}(\mathbf{x}) & \text{for } j = 1, \dots, J \\ & \mu_{x_n} \in [l_n, u_n], x_n = w_n(\vartheta) & \text{for } n = 1, \dots, N \end{cases} \quad (41)$$

The values chosen for the weights k_i and k_j - in Eq. 41 the subscripts o and c refer to the objectives and constraints, respectively - depend on the relative importance of the mean performance and its variability. In any case, the increase in computational cost for a RO (with respect to DO) is proportional to the number of samples required for UQ. In the presence of computationally expensive evaluations (such as in Computational Structural Mechanics or Fluid Dynamics), the problem can rapidly become very expensive, thus limiting the choice to the most affordable optimization approaches. One possible solution is to rely on gradient-based optimization methods, which are usually less expensive than meta-heuristic optimizers (such as Genetic Algorithms), while being only able to get to a local optimum.

1. Unconstrained Rosenbrock

The deterministic problem simply results in the minimization of Eq. 38, whereas the related stochastic problem becomes

$$\min F := \mu_f + 2\sigma_f. \quad (42)$$

2. Constrained Rosenbrock

Again, the deterministic function to be minimized is given by Eq. 38. The deterministic constraints are defined by

$$\begin{cases} g_1 := (x_1 - 1)^3 - x - 2 + 1 \leq 0 \\ g_2 := x_1 + x_2 - 2 \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (43)$$

The stochastic problem is then formulated as

$$\begin{cases} \min & F := \mu_f + 2\sigma_f \\ \text{s.t.} & G_1 := \mu_{g_1} - 0.65\sigma_{g_1} \geq 0 \\ & G_2 := \mu_{g_2} - 0.25\sigma_{g_2} \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (44)$$

3. Generalized Rosenbrock

The Rosenbrock function is generalized to five variables is now dealt with. Only the unconstrained optimization is addressed, so to keep the case simple and the computational time contained - even if an algebraic one, the case involves a significant number of calculations when it comes to bootstrap samples. For the deterministic optimization, minimization of Eq. 39 is required without any further constraint. The problem is again defined by Eq. 42.

C. Transonic NACA 0012 shape optimization

Algebraic cases are useful for sifting through different aspects of the numerical methods isolating their effects, and to extend testing to expansion orders and design space cardinalities otherwise out of reach because of the huge computational efforts required. Nevertheless, the paper is focused on the development of techniques to be used in real-world applications, which can become significantly challenging in Aeronautics. In consequence of the limited resources available at the time when the framework was first developed, a choice had to be made between uncertainty quantification based on a complex case, or optimization based on a simple geometry and a limited number of design parameters. The second choice was preferred because of the opportunity to put all the framework's component to the test at once.

Fig. 4 Source RAE 2822 and baseline NACA 0012 computational meshes.

Central to the employment of the in-house code to Aeronautics applications is currently SU2 [73–75], an open-source framework for computational analysis and design having the purpose of providing state-of-the-art tools in a multi-physics context and being particularly devoted to Aerospace applications. Other than a density-based (natively compressible) CFD solver, SU2 provides a continuous Adjoint solver from the beginning and, most importantly for the applications of interest for this work, a discrete Adjoint solver became available as well in recent times [76, 77]. A number of useful routines for design optimization, including geometry parameterization and mesh deformation algorithms, are included as well.

The shape optimization of a NACA 0012 airfoil under transonic conditions is presented. In order to highlight the fundamental difference between a deterministic and a robust optimization, UQ is enforced for all the points explored by the optimizer also for the former, as for the generalized Rosenbrock function. The case has been built so to be reproducible for *a posteriori* comparisons with alternative methodologies and different frameworks by third parties. The mesh can be obtained using the SU2 deformation routines on the publicly available RAE 2822 airfoil mesh: it can be found in the RANS optimization subfolder of the official SU2 test cases and is described in [74] (section D1). Position of the points on the new airfoil were provided minimizing the distance with respect to points of the old one. Both the meshes are shown in Fig. 4.

Transonic conditions are assumed for the turbulent flow at Mach number $Ma = 0.68$ and Reynolds number $Re = 6.5 \times 10^6$. The Spalart-Allmaras (SA) turbulence model [78–80] is employed. The angle of attack for the baseline airfoil is fixed at $AoA = 1.55^\circ$. The following numerical settings were used: convective fluxes for the mean-flow equations are computed with the second-order JST centered spatial discretization scheme [81], employing the default values for the second- and fourth- order dissipation coefficients; convective fluxes for the turbulence equation employ a second-order scalar upwind scheme; convergence to the steady-state solution is obtained with implicit, local time-stepping. The flow solution for the datum geometry is shown in Fig. 5.

For the purpose of optimizing the shape of the airfoil, the geometry is parameterized by means of the point displacements in the y direction. Four points are used for the suction side and as many for the pressure side, without constraining the leading edge and trailing edge coordinates. y coordinates of the eight points are assumed to follow a truncated Gaussian distribution with variance $\sigma^2 = 0.5$. The design space is constrained bounding displacements to a maximum absolute value equal to 10% of the airfoil chord.

Mesh deformation is achieved in the framework employing RBF (Radial Basis Functions) interpolation [82, 83] for both two- and three-dimensional cases. Be $\mathbf{X} = \{X_i\}_{i=1}^d$ the coordinates of a generic mesh point in a d -dimensional space (\mathbb{R}^2 or \mathbb{R}^3), and $\{\mathbf{X}_{b_j}\}_{j=1}^{n_b}$ the sets of coordinates for n_b points placed along the boundary susceptible of shape optimization. A function having the form $\varphi(\mathbf{X}) = \varphi(\|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_{b_j}\|)$ is called radial basis function - it must be stressed that here $\|\cdot\|$ is not necessarily the Euclidean norm. The displacement of a domain point in response to displacements of the boundary points is described by an interpolation function in the form

Fig. 5 Baseline NACA-0012. Contours of Mach number.

$$S(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} a_j \varphi(\|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_{b_j}\|) + P(\mathbf{X}). \quad (45)$$

The unknowns, namely the coefficients a_j and the polynomial $P(\mathbf{X})$ - the latter being not mandatory -, can be computed enforcing the interpolation conditions $S(\mathbf{X}_{b_j}) = D_{b_j}$, where D_{b_j} is the (known) displacement of the point \mathbf{X}_{b_j} . It is then natural to parameterize the geometry using the displacements of a certain number of control point over the boundary as the design variables. Displacements at the internal mesh points will be then evaluated as $D(\mathbf{X}) = S(\mathbf{X})$. Note that no connectivity information is required, but only coordinates of mesh nodes: the method can be applied without knowing anything about the actual topology, only coordinates have to be accessed and substituted with the new ones.

The underlying theory, which can be retrieved in the cited references and resides beyond the scope of the paper, will not be discussed. For completeness, the employment of one of the Wendland's compact-support functions, well known for its capabilities and previously validated against Aerospace applications [84–88], is reported:

$$\varphi(r) = (1 - r)^4(4r + 1), \quad (46)$$

where $r = \|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_{b_j}\|$.

The QoIs are the lift coefficient C_L , the drag coefficient C_D and the ratio C_L/C_D between the two, whose nominal value is also the quantity to be maximized in the deterministic optimization. As for the robust optimization, the problem is reformulated as

$$\max F := \mu_{(C_L/C_d)} - 3\sigma_{(C_L/C_d)}. \quad (47)$$

V. Results

A. Ishigami

Results in Tab. 3 are computed by means of 13-th order PCEs. Exact moments are retrieved with all methods except for the gradient-enhanced Least Square surrogate, but the error is negligible and the saving in terms of required evaluations is more than enough for considering the results really good. Sensitivities also present slight deviations with regards to the exact values for Least Squares. It is interesting to note that the largest error (and the only significant one),

Table 3 Ishigami algebraic test case. Results for 13-th order PCEs.

(a)

	LSA	LSA-G	LSA2	LSA2-G	SGNI	SGNI-G	SGNI-F1	SGNI-F2
μ	3.5000	3.4997	3.5000	3.5000	3.5000	3.5000	3.5000	3.5000
σ	3.7208	3.7209	3.7208	3.7208	3.7208	3.7208	3.7208	3.7208
$\partial_1\mu$	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000
$\partial_2\mu$	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000
$\partial_3\mu$	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
$\partial_1\sigma$	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000
$\partial_2\sigma$	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000
$\partial_3\sigma$	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0285	0.0000
calls	840	210	840	840	19124	19124	76496	133868

(b)

	FFNI	FFNI-G	FFNI-F1	FFNI-F2	MCS
μ	3.5000	3.5000	3.5000	3.5000	3.5013 \pm 0.0042
σ	3.7208	3.7208	3.7208	3.7208	3.7205 \pm 0.0035
$\partial_1\mu$	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0001 \pm 0.0032
$\partial_2\mu$	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0002 \pm 0.0057
$\partial_3\mu$	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0001 \pm 0.0038
$\partial_1\sigma$	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0005 \pm 0.0040
$\partial_2\sigma$	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0002 \pm 0.0046
$\partial_3\sigma$	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0285	0.0000	0.0024 \pm 0.0067
calls	2745	2745	10977	19209	2000001

corresponding to the last derivative for standard deviation, is obtained when employing collocation methods in conjunction with one-sided finite differences. The accuracy of such scheme cannot be considered acceptable. It should be noted that the greater difficulties with $\partial_3\sigma$ are not incidental: the bootstrap results also show a larger degradation in the estimate of the quantity - one order of magnitude with respect to the other sensitivities -, reflecting the non-linear effects due to the fourth power in Eq. 32.

B. UQ1

A 4-th order expansion is enough to compute moments of the random output and their derivatives with a reasonable accuracy. Results are given in Tab. 4. LSA-G provides results not so different from those obtained with the other Least Squares surrogates, while reducing the number of evaluations by an order of magnitude. Moments are less accurate in comparison with LSA, whereas moment sensitivities are predicted with similar accuracy - but LSA2 and especially LSA2-G perform better. Collocation methods better agree with reference values, but the evaluations are increased in number by two orders of magnitude - three if finite differences are used for computing sensitivities. In this test, LSA2-G behaves almost the same as the sparse-grid PCEs, still being much more affordable. The performance offered by LSA-G is more than satisfying, considering that the computational cost is reduced by over 77 times with respect to SGNI-G. The approximation can be considered more than acceptable. If the differences between LSA-G and the sparse quadratures were more significant, LSA2-G could be considered a better compromise: at a cost over 10 times higher than LSA-G, the slight increase in accuracy could not justify the choice, especially if the evaluations were not algebraic. Gradient enhancement is then preferred. It should be noted that in this case, at the precision used for reporting the results, no difference is found for moment sensitivities among SGNI-G, SGNI-F1 and SGNI-F2.

Among the algebraic test cases presented in this work, UQ1 has the greater dimensionality. Opportunity is taken to show the effect of an increase in the oversampling level for Least Squares surrogates, in order to demonstrate that the present implementation is quite insensitive to the choice of a specific value: the random component in selection of the training points seems to be responsible for the fluctuations of the error in Fig. 6 more than the applied oversampling. Results for the gradient of the mean lead to similar conclusions and are then not reported. The partial improvements on the results are not worth the steep increase in the number of training points. $\zeta = 1.5$ is enough to ensure convergence to acceptable solutions for all the cases, while keeping the number of deterministic evaluations fairly low. Finally,

Table 4 UQ1 algebraic test case. Results for 4-th order PCEs.

	LSA	LSA-G	LSA2	LSA2-G	SGNI	SGNI-G	SGNI-F1	SGNI-F2	MCS
μ	0.2189	0.2186	0.2190	0.2190	0.2189	0.2189	0.2189	0.2189	0.2189 \pm 0.0002
σ	0.1551	0.1549	0.1552	0.1552	0.1553	0.1553	0.1553	0.1553	0.1553 \pm 0.0002
$\partial_1\mu$	0.0937	0.0937	0.0938	0.0939	0.0938	0.0938	0.0941	0.0938	0.0938 \pm 0.0001
$\partial_2\mu$	0.0267	0.0266	0.0268	0.0268	0.0268	0.0268	0.0268	0.0268	0.0268 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_3\mu$	0.0357	0.0358	0.0358	0.0358	0.0357	0.0357	0.0357	0.0357	0.0358 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_4\mu$	0.0536	0.0536	0.0536	0.0536	0.0536	0.0536	0.0536	0.0536	0.0536 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_5\mu$	0.0268	0.0267	0.0268	0.0268	0.0268	0.0268	0.0268	0.0268	0.0268 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_6\mu$	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0106	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_7\mu$	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_8\mu$	-0.0106	-0.0106	-0.0106	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107	-0.0107 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_9\mu$	-0.0205	-0.0206	-0.0205	-0.0206	-0.0206	-0.0206	-0.0206	-0.0206	-0.0206 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_{10}\mu$	-0.0206	-0.0205	-0.0205	-0.0206	-0.0206	-0.0206	-0.0206	-0.0206	-0.0206 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_1\sigma$	0.0504	0.0504	0.0507	0.0507	0.0506	0.0507	0.0508	0.0507	0.0507 \pm 0.0001
$\partial_2\sigma$	0.0084	0.0083	0.0084	0.0084	0.0084	0.0084	0.0084	0.0084	0.0084 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_3\sigma$	0.0192	0.0192	0.0192	0.0192	0.0192	0.0192	0.0192	0.0192	0.0193 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_4\sigma$	0.0120	0.0121	0.0121	0.0121	0.0121	0.0121	0.0121	0.0121	0.0121 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_5\sigma$	0.0139	0.0142	0.0140	0.0140	0.0140	0.0140	0.0140	0.0140	0.0140 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_6\sigma$	-0.0079	-0.0079	-0.0079	-0.0080	-0.0079	-0.0080	-0.0080	-0.0080	-0.0080 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_7\sigma$	-0.0079	-0.0079	-0.0079	-0.0080	-0.0079	-0.0080	-0.0080	-0.0080	-0.0080 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_8\sigma$	-0.0077	-0.0079	-0.0079	-0.0080	-0.0079	-0.0080	-0.0080	-0.0080	-0.0080 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_9\sigma$	-0.0154	-0.0155	-0.0154	-0.0155	-0.0154	-0.0155	-0.0155	-0.0155	-0.0155 \pm 0.0000
$\partial_{10}\sigma$	-0.0154	-0.0155	-0.0154	-0.0155	-0.0154	-0.0155	-0.0155	-0.0155	-0.0155 \pm 0.0000
calls	1501	137	1501	1501	10626	10626	116886	223146	5500001

it should be noted that UQ1 was formulated so to offer a representative number of sensitivities for comparing their behaviors, and at the same time tighten enough confidence intervals for the bootstrap results: the conclusions are meaningful only because of the small uncertainty associated with the reference values.

C. UQ2

The results, reported in Tab. 5, essentially confirm the trends observed in the first two cases. The larger confidence intervals make more difficult to directly compare the numbers, but a few points become immediately noticeable, given also the previous results:

- LSA is not particularly preferable in comparison with the other methods: even if it is significantly cheaper than quadrature-based methods at the cost of a degraded accuracy, it does not perform systematically better than the more efficient LSA-G, and it is clearly outperformed by LSA2 and LSA2-G for the same expensiveness. The disadvantages are directly related to the fact that no derivative information is employed for either enhancing the PCE expansion or improving computation of moment sensitivities.
- One-sided finite differences in conjunction with Collocation methods are not a reliable choice. As for the Ishigami function - even if with lesser evidence -, a deviation in values of the moment sensitivities is observed when employing quadratures only for such choice. It could be argued that the fact depends on the non-optimal choice of the discretization interval, but the same interval is used for two-sided differences, which instead offer almost perfect matching with the results obtained by inclusion of the gradients, for all the cases. Also, in real-life cases there might not be room for addressing a separate convergence study: some degree of independence from the discretization interval is indeed desirable.
- Since in the algebraic cases function sensitivities are exact, it follows from the previous point that two-sided finite differences do not introduce a meaningful error, but at the same time their expensiveness is not justified if the provided gradient information is accurate enough. In real-life applications, this means that capabilities of the employed Adjoint solver are crucial when relying on Collocation methods.
- Since LSA-G maximizes the efficiency at the expense of accuracy and some degree of approximation is always involved, quality of the provided derivative information is even more fundamental for this method: were the gradients not accurate, not only the moment sensitivities, but all results computed through the surrogate expansion would be severely affected. The discussed Least Squares surrogates are efficient, but the UQ code has to be supported by the other framework components in order to avoid the approximation to become too rough.

Fig. 6 UQ1 algebraic test case. Effects of the oversampling level on Least Squares surrogates.

Table 5 UQ2 algebraic test case. Results for 6-th order PCEs.

	LSA	LSA-G	LSA2	LSA2-G	SGNI	SGNI-G	SGNI-F1	SGNI-F2	MCS
μ	6.4478	6.4418	6.4360	6.4360	6.4399	6.4399	6.4399	6.4399	6.4386 \pm 0.0050
σ	4.4971	4.4970	4.4971	4.4971	4.4972	4.4972	4.4972	4.4972	4.4979 \pm 0.0044
$\partial_1 \mu$	0.9270	0.9310	0.9338	0.9277	0.9277	0.9277	0.9277	0.9277	0.9277 \pm 0.0009
$\partial_2 \mu$	0.1793	0.1749	0.1784	0.1854	0.1792	0.1792	0.1760	0.1793	0.1792 \pm 0.0018
$\partial_3 \mu$	0.3998	0.4004	0.4009	0.4000	0.4000	0.4000	0.4000	0.4000	0.4003 \pm 0.0007
$\partial_4 \mu$	2.8929	2.8937	2.8924	2.8923	2.8923	2.8923	2.8923	2.8923	2.8929 \pm 0.0010
$\partial_5 \mu$	0.3251	0.3248	0.3225	0.3243	0.3243	0.3243	0.3242	0.3243	0.3243 \pm 0.0004
$\partial_1 \sigma$	0.5816	0.5868	0.5849	0.5876	0.5880	0.5879	0.5882	0.5879	0.5876 \pm 0.0012
$\partial_2 \sigma$	0.8252	0.8266	0.8273	0.8247	0.8254	0.8257	0.8272	0.8257	0.8260 \pm 0.0019
$\partial_3 \sigma$	0.4111	0.4103	0.4103	0.4124	0.4119	0.4119	0.4123	0.4119	0.4127 \pm 0.0012
$\partial_4 \sigma$	0.1640	0.1652	0.1643	0.1657	0.1654	0.1654	0.1662	0.1654	0.1659 \pm 0.0014
$\partial_5 \sigma$	0.2594	0.2591	0.2563	0.2597	0.2596	0.2596	0.2595	0.2596	0.2597 \pm 0.0004
calls	693	115	693	693	7997	7997	47982	87967	3000001

Table 6 Unconstrained Rosenbrock algebraic test case. Results for 4-th order PCEs.

(a)

	LSA	LSA-G	LSA2	LSA2-G	SGNI	SGNI-G	SGNI-F1	SGNI-F2
μ_{x_1}	0.0008	0.0008	0.0008	0.0008	0.0008	0.0008	-0.0040	0.0008
μ_{x_2}	1.8488	1.8488	1.8488	1.8488	1.8488	1.8488	1.8438	1.8488
μ_{f_1}	374.0430	374.0430	374.0440	374.0440	374.0440	374.0440	373.2110	374.0430
σ_{f_1}	689.7590	689.7590	689.7580	689.7580	689.7580	689.7580	690.2120	689.7590
<i>OBJ</i>	1753.5600	1753.5600	1753.5600	1753.5600	1753.5600	1753.5600	1753.6300	1753.5600
calls	193	75	218	218	550	550	1485	2750

(b)

	FFNI	FFNI-G	FFNI-F1	FFNI-F2	DET	MCS
μ_{x_1}	0.0008	0.0008	-0.0040	0.0008	1.0000	0.0025
μ_{x_2}	1.8488	1.8488	1.8438	1.8488	1.0000	1.8465
μ_{f_1}	374.0440	374.0440	373.2110	374.0430	801.0000	373.0960
σ_{f_1}	689.7580	689.7580	690.2120	689.7590	2223.5100	683.5230
<i>OBJ</i>	1753.5600	1753.5600	1753.6300	1753.5600	0.0000	1740.1400
calls	250	250	675	1250	25	1.8e+08

D. Rosenbrock

Results for the unconstrained, constrained, and generalized Rosenbrock optimizations are shown in Tab. 6, 7, and 8. They will be discussed together. Difference between the deterministic optimum and the robust optima is very large, as expected. The two-dimensional problems show a reduced advantage of Least Squares surrogates against the other methods in terms of efficiency, but this is only due to the low dimensionality, and the advantage is again increased for the 5-dimensional problem. The number of employed bootstrap samples is too low for MCS, what is most evident in the constrained case since the constraints are violated, but better accuracy would have required extended computational times and the use of the method as a reference loses some meaning for optimization. Again, the one-sided finite differences affect the computation of moment sensitivities leading to different (worse) optima, but not for the constrained case. All the other methods perform exactly the same way: LSA-G gives the same results of the more expensive approaches, and is by far the most preferable.

E. Transonic NACA 0012 shape optimization

For this test case, computations with LSA and LSA-G have been done both with and without reuse of points. Although for the other approaches second-order PCEs were used, for SGNI-G the first order was preferred: in a real context, the number of simulations required for a second-order sparse-grid Collocation PCE can be overwhelming, and it is unlikely it would be used despite the superior accuracy. A standard second-order SGNI was also addressed so to demonstrate that the differences in the results are not worth the significantly higher computational cost: a first-order PCE is expected to lose some accuracy, but the information provided by the Adjoint solver helps in improving values of the moments' sensitivities, thus assisting the optimizer in reaching a similar optimum and a comparably robust final design. The results are summarized in Tab. 9 - note that the QoIs are indexed in the following order: C_L/C_D , C_L , C_D . It can be noted that values of the objective at the optima for robust computations are not significantly different from each other, with the greater deviation from the general trend showed by LSA-R (worst optimum) and LSA2-G (best optimum). The reuse of points affects the results especially for LSA-R, which reduces the required simulations almost to a third but seems to be responsible for a degradation of the performance with the method. LSA-G and LSA-GR show similar results, but the number of simulation, unexpectedly, is higher for LSA-GR, because of the more numerous iterations performed by the optimizer to reach the optimum: it would be difficult to guess if this is only related to the approximation introduced reusing the points. It is interesting to note that LSA2-G offers a good balance between expensiveness and performance, but it cannot be preferred to LSA-G or to the lower-order SGNI-G if severe limitations exist with regards to the computational resources. Differences among the optimal designs obtained with the employed methods are shown in Fig. 7 exasperating the proportions. Although the answers given by the methods are partially different, especially for the pressure side, all robust designs share similar characteristics when compared

Table 7 Constrained Rosenbrock algebraic test case. Results for 4-th order PCEs.

(a)

	LSA	LSA-G	LSA2	LSA2-G	SGNI	SGNI-G	SGNI-F1	SGNI-F2
μ_{x_1}	-0.1577	-0.1577	-0.1577	-0.1577	-0.1577	-0.1577	-0.1577	-0.1577
μ_{x_2}	1.8041	1.8041	1.8041	1.8041	1.8041	1.8041	1.8041	1.8041
μ_{f_1}	373.0170	373.0170	373.0170	373.0170	373.0170	373.0170	373.0160	373.0170
μ_{f_2}	5.8289	5.8289	5.8289	5.8289	5.8289	5.8289	5.8289	5.8289
μ_{f_3}	0.3536	0.3536	0.3536	0.3536	0.3536	0.3536	0.3536	0.3536
σ_{f_1}	727.0370	727.0370	727.0370	727.0370	727.0370	727.0370	727.0360	727.0370
σ_{f_2}	8.9676	8.9676	8.9676	8.9676	8.9676	8.9676	8.9675	8.9676
σ_{f_3}	1.4142	1.4142	1.4142	1.4142	1.4142	1.4142	1.4142	1.4142
<i>OBJ</i>	1827.0900	1827.0900	1827.0900	1827.0900	1827.0900	1827.0900	1827.0900	1827.0900
<i>CONS</i> ₁	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000
<i>CONS</i> ₂	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000
calls	130	49	129	129	330	330	825	1650

(b)

	FFNI	FFNI-G	FFNI-F1	FFNI-F2	DET	MCS
μ_{x_1}	-0.1577	-0.1577	-0.1577	-0.1577	1.0000	-0.1603
μ_{x_2}	1.8041	1.8041	1.8041	1.8041	1.0000	1.8054
μ_{f_1}	373.0170	373.0170	373.0160	373.0170	801.0000	373.0920
μ_{f_2}	5.8289	5.8289	5.8289	5.8289	0.0000	5.8565
μ_{f_3}	0.3536	0.3536	0.3536	0.3536	0.0000	0.3555
σ_{f_1}	727.0370	727.0370	727.0360	727.0370	2223.5100	718.6980
σ_{f_2}	8.9676	8.9676	8.9675	8.9676	4.0000	9.0000
σ_{f_3}	1.4142	1.4142	1.4142	1.4142	1.4142	1.4138
<i>OBJ</i>	1827.0900	1827.0900	1827.0900	1827.0900	0.0000	1810.4900
<i>CONS</i> ₁	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0065
<i>CONS</i> ₂	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0021
calls	150	150	375	750	25	4.95e+08

Table 8 Generalized Rosenbrock algebraic test case. Results for 4-th order PCEs.

	LSA	LSA-G	LSA2	LSA2-G	SGNI	SGNI-G	SGNI-F1	SGNI-F2	DET	MCS
μ_{x_1}	0.0009	0.0009	0.0009	0.0009	0.0009	0.0009	-0.0032	0.0009	1.0000	-0.0063
μ_{x_2}	0.1186	0.1186	0.1186	0.1186	0.1186	0.1186	0.1146	0.1186	1.0000	0.1348
μ_{x_3}	0.1279	0.1279	0.1279	0.1279	0.1279	0.1279	0.1240	0.1279	1.0000	0.1107
μ_{x_4}	0.1893	0.1893	0.1893	0.1893	0.1893	0.1893	0.1851	0.1893	1.0000	0.1518
μ_{x_5}	1.6551	1.6551	1.6551	1.6551	1.6551	1.6551	1.6480	1.6551	1.0001	1.4579
μ_{f_1}	1496.6700	1496.6700	1496.6700	1496.6700	1496.6700	1496.6700	1496.3800	1496.6700	3204.0300	1478.9200
σ_{f_1}	2051.9300	2051.9300	2051.9300	2051.9300	2051.9300	2051.9300	2052.1500	2051.9300	4420.1300	2064.0300
<i>OBJ</i>	5600.5200	5600.5200	5600.5200	5600.5200	5600.5200	5600.5200	5600.6800	5600.5200	0.0000	5606.9900
calls	4231	643	4158	4158	22022	22022	486486	242242	146875	9e+08

Table 9 Results for the NACA 0012 airfoil.

	LSA	LSA-R	LSA-G	LSA-GR	LSA2	LSA2-G	SGNI	SGNI-G	DET
μ_{x_1}	5.3841	6.1924	7.7750	7.5706	7.3931	9.0939	6.8941	6.1709	14.5981
μ_{x_2}	10.9092	11.3742	13.2904	12.3834	11.5782	13.6389	12.4518	12.5945	18.8218
μ_{x_3}	5.4938	6.3202	7.0321	5.5346	4.4874	7.1403	6.7606	7.5744	7.8281
μ_{x_4}	-19.8913	-20.0000	-19.8243	-19.8986	-20.0000	-19.1763	-19.8602	-19.3636	-20.0000
μ_{x_5}	-8.0417	-6.3727	-2.3242	-3.2248	-6.8094	-2.5907	-5.5948	-2.4824	-4.5245
μ_{x_6}	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000	19.9247	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000
μ_{x_7}	20.0000	17.7361	20.0000	20.0000	19.7387	20.0000	19.9677	20.0000	20.0000
μ_{x_8}	12.8464	9.6886	14.0001	11.4062	12.5230	14.2719	10.9888	14.8493	20.0000
μ_{f_1}	56.2505	55.9723	56.4336	56.4742	56.5906	56.7552	56.5512	56.1790	55.7319
μ_{f_2}	0.6006	0.5971	0.5953	0.5863	0.5960	0.5985	0.6006	0.5934	0.6391
μ_{f_3}	0.0107	0.0107	0.0105	0.0104	0.0105	0.0105	0.0106	0.0106	0.0114
σ_{f_1}	0.2253	0.2854	0.2808	0.3231	0.3254	0.3164	0.2809	0.2151	1.1852
σ_{f_2}	0.0060	0.0060	0.0056	0.0055	0.0062	0.0063	0.0062	0.0061	0.0079
σ_{f_3}	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002
<i>OBJ</i>	55.5744	55.1160	55.5911	55.5050	55.6143	55.8061	55.7084	55.5337	59.6820
calls	3864	1375	309	351	3366	1876	9333	425	629

to the deterministic optimal design. The greater deviations are seen in proximity of the trailing edge, where different methods produce designs which deviate from the deterministic optimum approaching it from both sides. Contours of Mach numbers for comparing the flow solutions are shown in Fig. 8 for the deterministic optimization and in Fig. 9 for robust optimizations, respectively. It is easy to notice the double shock which forms on the suction side for the robust designs. It would be interesting, in future, to study the effective implementation of constraints targeted to enforce - or, conversely, to avoid - some aerodynamic features of the flow. Finally, Fig. 10 shows the evolution of the optimal design for both deterministic and robust optimizations. The increased robustness with respect to the deterministic optimization is evident.

In summary, all the approaches lead to comparable results, but they require very diverse amounts of resources. LSA-G does not perform worse than LSA while providing a considerably greater efficiency. Fewer simulations were required also in comparison with the lower-order SGNI-G, which led to a slightly worse optimum. The saving is most evident comparing the number of simulations used by SGNI, over thirty times higher. From the results it is not clear if the reuse of points is really effective, but the value chosen for the related tolerance could be the reason - or one of the many - behind the increased expensiveness of LSA-GR, involving greater difficulties for the optimizer to find the route to the optimum. The greatest advantage is obtained employing the gradient-enhanced surrogates: exploiting the Adjoint sensitivities to enrich the approximated expansion and reduce the number of solver runs by $(n + 1)$ times, while relying on the surrogate expansion for computing moments' sensitivities, is demonstrated to be a successful approach.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7 Comparison of robust designs with the baseline airfoil and the deterministic optimum.

Fig. 8 Optimal nominal design. Contours of Mach number.

VI. Conclusion

The advantages of Non-Intrusive Polynomial Chaos approaches based on Least Squares surrogates and gradient-enhanced expansions have been discussed. Comparison with quadrature-based methods clearly shows the benefits in terms of computational time reduction, still preserving a reasonable accuracy for practical applications. Freedom in the choice of evaluation points for Least Squares surrogates is exploited so to further reduce the number of calculations involved: deterministic evaluation can be reused when the points have equal or very near coordinates in the design space, capability of noteworthy importance when dealing with Robust Optimization and uniquely available with regression-based methods. All tests were performed relying upon an in-house framework built with modularity in mind but presently being rather a prototype, whose development and re-implementation in some efficient compiled language is planned for the future. Following the preliminary results shown in this paper, more advanced tests of industrial interests are also planned, together with improvements of the numerical methods and algorithms - and the introduction of new ones -, for which the framework is going to be a suitable test bench.

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Fig. 9 Optimal robust designs obtained with gradient-enhanced PCE or inclusion of derivative information. Contours of Mach number.

(a) Deterministic optimization.

(b) Robust optimization. LSA-G.

(c) Robust optimization. LSA2.

(d) Robust optimization. LSA2-G.

(e) Robust optimization. SGNI.

(f) Robust optimization. SGNI-G.

Fig. 10 Evolution of optimal design during the optimization.

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